

Business Strategy of a Graphic Designing Company in Japan Owned by Nepalese Immigrant Businessman

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Abstract:- The success of a menu and flyer-designing enterprise owned by an immigrant businessman from Nepal and operating in Japan relies on many crucial elements. The first consideration is the importance of cultural sensitivity and comprehension. The firm owner and designers must comprehensively understand Japanese food culture's traditional and contemporary dimensions, owing to the multifaceted nature and intricacies inherent in Japanese cuisine. The main focus of the study is to examine the success factor of a menu and flyer design company owned by a Nepalese immigrant businessman in Japan. In addition, the study also focuses on identifying and understanding the specific target market for the menu and flyer design company, including restaurants, cafes, and other businesses in Japan. It explores the preferences and requirements of the target market regarding menu and flyer designs. Lastly, the study thoroughly analyzes the competitive landscape in Japan's menu and flyer design industry.

Keywords:- Graphic design, Nepalese graphic designing entrepreneurs in Japan, Nepalese Restaurant in Japan, Retention of Nepalese in Japan.

I. INTRODUCTION

A menu is not just about providing information about the item sailing by the Company through pictures, fonts, and colors; it is also the creative output of the graphic designers. That is why there is a deep relationship between the consumer's desire and the expressions of the designers, whose ultimate objective is to communicate clearly and understandably to the customer about the product. Graphic designers use pens, pencils, chalk, etc., for direct hand-drawn design, and digital tools such as Photoshop, Illustrator, InDesign, PowerPoint, and many more tools are used for paper printing and digital menus. Graphic design influences a wide range of fields, such as politics, business, and entire society. Graphic design reflects people, issues, and events and communicates ideas and perceptions of the people, because society is reflected in design, and design, in turn, reflects society (Amy, 2021).

In today's modern era, menus have evolved beyond traditional paper and board with the evolution of mobile devices and computers. Restaurant menus, whether analog or digital, are one of the essential strategic tools for the restaurant industry. (Reynolds & Taylor, 2009).

If we turn the paper back to the history of the menu, it has an old history. The term "menu" has its origins in the Latin word "minutus," which translates to "small" (Kotschevar & Withrow, 2007).

The idea of menu originated around 1100 CE, during the Song Dynasty in China (Debczak, 2022).

The menus of good restaurants display the selection of foods offered by the chef (Luebbers, 1978). Among the menus, the descriptive menu has a more significant impact on the restaurant business. A descriptive menu plays a role in increasing food sales, restaurant attitudes, and creating regular customers. Moreover, descriptive menu labels are significant for customers to calculate calories (Wansink et al., 2005). The detailed description of the menu helps to create an image in the consumer's mind and supports their decisions to select the food positively (Shoemaker et al., 2005).

Digital menus are also increasingly prevalent from the point of view of health consciousness. Whether on the paper menu or digitally, a description of calorie information accompanies each menu item. Moreover, another thing that needs to be added here is that various languages are on the digital menu. Regarding the paper menu, we can find two languages: local language and English. It helps the customers select items and helps the business enhance. Because of the multi-language menu, it breaks the communication barrier between customers and restaurant staff.

II. NEPALESE IN JAPAN

The number of foreign residents in Japan rises yearly and has risen by 7.3% over the prior year. However, Nepalese started to come to Japan one century ago as students in different disciplines. According to Basnet and Kago (2023), there were 139,393 Nepalese immigrants residing in Japan at the end of 2022, but in only six months 12.2% increase and reached 156,333 Nepalese immigrants as of the end of June 2020.

In these, Nepalese entrepreneurs are also increasing. They are engaged in various business sectors, such as remittance businesses, halal food grocery stores, restaurants, and graphic design companies. Among various sectors, the restaurant business is popular among the Nepalese community. Despite Nepal being a small country compared to India and China, it has a diverse ethnic group and unique culinary traditions. In Japan, ethnic Nepalese groups operate ethnic restaurants such as Thakali Restaurants and Newari Restaurants. Nepalese food is trendy all over the world.

Recently, Nepalese chef Santosh Shah, based in London, became the second runner-up in 2020 and winner of the UK's reality cookery TV series, BBC Master Chef¹, for representing typical Nepalese food. In the same way, the graphic designing Company is also famous among Nepalese. The graphic designing company owner has a student background and a good command of Japanese. The Japanese language gives them strong support to enhance business and help Nepalese Restaurant owners' language problems. However, in this study, we focus on a graphic design company operated by Nepalese in Japan, their unique business strategy opportunities, and the problems faced by graphic design.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study examines the success factor of a menu and flyer designing Company owned by a Nepalese immigrant businessman in Japan. In addition, the study also focuses on the specific target market for the menu and flyer-designing Company, including restaurants, grocery stores, and other businesses in Japan. Also, it explores the preferences and requirements of the target market regarding menu and flyer designs. Lastly, it thoroughly analyzes the competitive landscape in Japan's menu and flyer design industry.

The main focus of the study is to examine the success factor of a menu and flyer designing Company owned by former Nepalese Students in Japan. In addition, the study also focuses on:

To identify and understand the specific target market for the menu and flyer-designing companies, including restaurants, cafes, and other businesses in Japan.

- To explore the preferences and requirements of the target market regarding menu and flyer designs.
- To thoroughly analyze Japan's competitive landscape in the menu and flyer design industry.

IV. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In this, we are targeting to create three Research questions such as,

- What are the challenges faced by graphic designing companies in Japan owned by Nepalese entrepreneurs?
- What factors affect the decision-making in selecting the graphic designing services of a Nepalese-owned graphic designing business in Japan?
- What might be the key factors of success for Nepalese graphic designing companies owned by Nepalese entrepreneurs in Japan?

V. RESEARCH GAP

Nepalese operate different kinds of business in Japan, such as restaurant business, delivery companies(necessary items for restaurants such as spices, rice, meat, flour, etc.),

Halal food² stores, Remittance, graphic designing (menu, flyers, hoarding board, etc.) companies, international schools and many more. Nepalese people grew by approximately 396% from 2013(31,537) to the end of June 2023(156,333). Nepalese enter as students to work in a Japanese company, cook, have a dependent (family) visa, etc. There has already been researched the migration of Nepalese cooks from Malma village of Nepal to Japan to work in restaurants (Kharel, 2016), cook conditions in Japan (Gyawali& Tanaka, 2022), Indo-Nepal Restaurants in Japan(Kobayashi, 2022), operational resiliencies and service recovery strategies of Nepalese restaurants owners during the COVID-19 (Basnet &Kago, 2023), immigration policies on former student's career (Basnet &Kago, 2023), Nepalese student life in Japan(Morita, 2017). In 2016, the number of Nepalese restaurants was more than 3,000 (Karel, 2016), while the Nepalese population at the end of 2016 was 67,470. Accordingly, the dream of Nepalese cooks in Japan is to be a restaurant owner (Gyawali& Masako, 2022). The data indicates that restaurant numbers might be more than 5000. The menu is the face of the restaurants, and customers order items using digital or paper menus, helping to enhance the restaurant business. However, there has yet to be research on graphic design. It is worth researching graphic design companies.

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. An outline of the menu and flyer designs

According to Antun& Gustafson (2005), in recent times, there has been an increasing scholarly focus on restaurant menus, possibly stemming from the belief that menus play a vital role in the success of restaurants. The study of menu design has recently emerged as a sub-field of research in the mainstream menu literature, attracting the attention of menu researchers and signaling a growing interest in this area. This is evidenced by the works of Bowen and Morris (1995), Choi et al. (2010), Kincaid &Corsun (2003), Reynolds et al. (2005), Sobol& Barry (1980), and Yang (2012), the arrangement of a menu display has garnered significant attention from scholars in this particular field. Furthermore, other areas exist where menu' design has been examined. Shoemaker et al. (2005) have investigated the impact of menu descriptions on customers' item selections. Subsequently, Lockyer (2006), and Wansink et al. (2001) have directed their attention toward examining menu labels and their influence on the selection of items from the menu. Dayan and Bar-Hillel (2011) noted limited research on placing menu items within a category list. Studies by Choi et al. (2010). Reynolds et al. (2005) have examined the correlation between the design elements of a menu card and the sales of items.

According to Mills & Thomas (2008), menu information has been scrutinized through consumer perception. In addition to research studies, consultants and professionals also focus on menu design issues. They emphasize that the design of a menu display offers restaurateurs the chance to anticipate and enhance

¹ Santosh Shah winner of MasterChef the Professionals Rematch 2021 | Full Performance | Final Episode <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K3TmHMzOPQ4>

²Halal food: Halal food is a permissible item to consume in the Islamic religion.

customers' item-ordering behavior.

B. Development of migrant-owned businesses in Japan

In 2008, as part of the "10 thousand International Students Plan" to develop human resources in developing countries and the "Global Strategy" to expand the flow of people, goods, money, and information between Asia and the world (Tsukada & Ota, 2018). The "30 thousand International Students Plan" was launched in 2008 (Yonezawa, 2019). We were aiming for a plan for all people. The rapid increase in Nepalese can impact the Japanese government's international student program. Similarly, there are also Nepali nationals who enter the country on skilled visas and dependent visas. In addition, the number of Nepali nationals has been increasing since the introduction of the new special skills visa system, and the number will continue to increase. After graduating from school or university, international students choose to find employment in Japan. Some former Nepali students have become entrepreneurs independently after graduating or working in Japan for several years.

Among Nepalese entrepreneurs, there are also Nepali business owners who design menus and flyers. This study will study the factors behind the success of menu and flyer design companies.

In the case of other Asian countries, it also has the same story to increase the population in Japan as an immigrant. According to Waldinger (1994), between 1991 and 2004, around 10,000 students from Bangladesh, in addition to the migrant population, pursued their studies in Japan. Bangladesh immigrants also from East Asia and operating various businesses which can be classified into two main categories: non-traditional ventures encompassing calling card services, used car trade, electronics trade, and ethnic magazine publication; and traditional enterprises comprising halal food establishments, restaurants, and travel agencies. (Watanabe, 1998). Regarding Halal food establishment, because of the arrival of Muslim migrants from South Asia and Iran during the early 1980s (Wilson & Portes, 1980). According to Kloosterman et al. (1999), The educational backgrounds and commercial motivations of Bangladeshi calling card traders, namely Ryo International and Sadiatec, indicate that they had prior exposure to information technology before relocating to Japan.

Nevertheless, in the case of Nepalese, the restaurant business is famous among Nepalese communities. The number of Nepalese immigrant entrepreneurs is increasing daily because of their academic background and motivation to grab business opportunities. Moreover, restaurants are increasing significantly. According to Kharel (2016), some companies, such as consultancy and graphic designing companies, are helping immigrants start restaurants with services, including consultation, selling groceries, graphic design, printing, and advertising. According to Faist & Ozveren (2004), due to the relatively higher cost of Indian cuisine than local restaurant cuisine to call customers, they started advertising strategies, such as disseminating

brochures, posters, and handouts at subway stations and signboards in Japanese and English.

VII. HYPOTHESIS

- H1. There are no retention issues for Nepalese working in Japan.
- H2. Services specializing in graphic design are the success factor of a menu and flyer design company owned by a Nepali entrepreneur.
- H3. Nepalese restaurant owners require unique menu designs, which are challenging to get from Japanese design companies.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

The study mainly focuses on the quantitative aspect to understand the success factor of a menu and flyer designing Company adopted and owned by a Nepali immigrant businessman in Japan. Apart from this, the study is descriptive so that it helps fundamentally define the research problem, understand the research aims, and examine the business studies adopted by the food industry in the Japanese market. To collect the data, the primary data collection method will be best suited to the study. It includes the data collected the first time by asking questions from the respondent in a survey or interview. In the current study to examine the types and menu design and also focus on the development of immigrant entrepreneurship in Japan, the study mainly focuses on surveying by developing a semi-structured close-ended questionnaire that includes multiple types of questions related to the barriers, size, and what are the challenges faced by the companies in Japan market. It also discusses the sample size of 3-5 to help understand the data by collecting large numbers. This will help understand the outcome of international migration, which has affected many aspects of their receiving society. The simple random sampling method is to be used so that the researcher can collect a small number of units in a given population in a limited period, which will help collect a large number of data in a short period. The process requires 10 to 15 minutes per person, so the researcher will collect the database on the research aims and objectives. It includes face-to-face interviews or Google forms so that the data will be collected validly.

IX. MOTIVATION TOWARDS GRAPHIC DESIGNING BUSINESS IN JAPAN

The article provides insights into Japan's five Nepalese-owned graphic design businesses: GMT International Co. Ltd, Kings Design, ZOOM Co., Ltd, Sinka Co., Ltd, and BLUESKY Company. It does not mean that, above five companies lead the business of graphic design in Japan. Some of freelancer designers are also engage in designing field. Each business faces unique challenges, as does the nature of the graphic design industry in Japan. Here is the survey with five designing company in Japan

Here is the survey result as a digital version of a paper survey report.

Table 1: Overview of the Interviewee's Responses

Gmt international co. Ltd (Mr.TilakMalla)	
Note: Over 2,500 design experiences, including restaurant menus and other events (weddings, birthday parties, festivals, etc.)	
Challenges	Unhealthy Competition from former employees. Newcomers can also start quickly without research. As a result, pricing is the same. Many Nepalese talent and owners are also moving to the third country.
Opportunities	Growing Business Business Opportunities
Reason to Start Business	The number of Nepali business owners in Japan was increasing, but due to language and other reasons, they needed help to request the necessary designs from Japanese design companies. I have been involved in media activities in Japan for a long time. I was asked to help with the design. That voice was a motivating factor in starting my own graphic design business.
Future Plan	Expand business in Nepal as an outsourcing to provide quick services.
Kings Design(OffshoreworksCo.,Ltd) Mr. Sandesh Adhikari	
Note: Over 1,500 design experiences, including restaurant menus and other events (weddings, birthday parties, festivals, etc.)	
Challenges	Unhealthy Competition from within a graphic designing company owned by Nepalese Customers often request corrections even after final confirmation In addition to design, we receive other requests and consultations (interpreters, translation of documents written in Japanese, etc.) A newcomer can also start quickly without research. As a result, there is no similarity in pricing. Restaurant owners and cooks (future possible restaurant owners) are moving to third countries.
Opportunities	We are helping them with other services such as translation and documentation and maintaining good customer relations. Business Opportunities
Reason to Start Business	I had experience working at a design company before starting a company. Working experience was a motivation factor in starting the company. Photography skills also motivated me to start this business.
Future Plan	As we move into the digital era, we intend to incorporate technology into graphic design.
ZOON Co.,Ltd (Mr. Suman Khadka)	
Note: Over 500 design experiences, including restaurant menus and other events (weddings, birthday parties, festivals, etc.)	
Challenges	Despite the ongoing progression of the digital era, customer awareness has mostly stayed the same. Customers choose a company with the cost of price or relationship rather than the basis of excellent design. Many clients have moved to third-world countries, and the trend is ongoing.
Opportunities	Endless business chances You can quickly grab other services such as business registration, visa support, etc.
Reason to Start Business	Mobile Applications, E-commerce Solutions, Web design, and Web applications are our company's primary services. However, I started designing a business to respond to customers' requests. Currently, our company helps our clients with business registration and provides other services specifically to the needs of restaurant owners.
Future Plan	Go down the path of digital platforms
SinkaCo.,Ltd (Mr. Naresh Basnet)	
Over 1,000 design experiences, including restaurant menus and other events (weddings, birthday parties, festivals, etc.)	
Challenges	The restaurant owners need more information and an idea of what kind of menu they want. We are getting only memo to create design rather than any idea and concept. Besides designing, most of the time, I get requests such as form fill-up, translation, and different types of bills from government sectors of Japan.
Opportunities	We are getting many foreign countries visa support while supporting documentation and requesting to find an IELTS online class somewhere. That is why we started new services in collaboration with educational institutions in India and Nepal to provide them with English class services. New business chances according to the customers' needs. Sometimes, customers are advised to start new services they need. Recently started an IELTS online class in collaboration with an institution
Reason to Start Business	Some of my friends requested to find a design company and visa documents services. While I got a good number of inquiries, I started the company. Getting a large number of foreign country visa support while supporting graphic designing services and

	documentation, they are requesting to find an IELTS online class somewhere. That is why we started new services in collaboration with educational institutions in India and Nepal to provide them with English class services. This kind of request from Nepalese communities motivated me to start a graphic company.
Future Plan	Documentation support and online English language services, including graphic design, are provided for those who are moving to a third country.
Bluesky Company (Mr. Lil Bahadur ThapaChhetri)	
Over 400+ design experiences, including restaurant menus and other services (weddings, birthday parties, festivals, etc.)	
Challenges	Conversion starts with the price of one menu design rather than the portfolio.
Opportunities	Business chances,
Reason to Start Business	Thousands of restaurant owners are from Baglungdistrict of Nepal. Because of Mr. Chhetri`sJapanese language ability and interest in design, his brother Mr. Lal Bahadur ThapaChhetri and sister in law BeluKhadkaThapa sent him for graphic training by paying them self. With the motivation of his family member and some of the owners of hisdistrict Mr. Chhetri started designing company and within 2 years designed for more than 400+ restaurants.According to Mr. Chhetri, his brother is operating a restaurant business in Japan and paying money for designing. His brother paying god amont money yearly and motivated him designing business might be good business in Japan among Nepalese immigrants. The need for graphic designing motivated him to take graphic training, and I learned graphic designing and all related work. I took one year of graphic work training and started my own business. There are thousands of restaurant owners in my area. I started this business two years ago.
Future Plan	Expand my work all over Japan

Sources: Created by the author based on Interview

Mr. TilakMalla is a CEO of GMT International Co. Ltd, famous in his graphic designing work and media publication. Mr. TilakMalla is known for his media publication know as Samudraprari newspaper. Most of the Nepalese immigrants in Japan know about his brand name samudrapari in Japan. Mr. Malla has experiences with over 2,500 design experiences, the Company faces challenges of unhealthy competition, data management problems by former staff, and the migration of clients to third countries.

The restaurant owner could not deal with a Japanese design company because of language barriers and asked for help designing menus, flyers, and signboards for a new restaurant business. The owners' words were a motivating factor for starting the design business.

However, it recognizes opportunities for business growth and has been interviewed on Japanese television several times for its media activities and graphic work. Nepalese restaurant owners require item names and explanations in two languages (Japanese and English), which is difficult for a Japanese design company and would be costly for my Nepalese designing company. That is why the Nepalese restaurant owner community and The Company aim to expand in Nepal.

Mr. Sandesh Adhikari is the CEO of Offshore Works Co. Ltd and operates a graphic designing company named Kings Design in Japan. In his more than ten years of residency in Japan, he supported 1,000+ restaurants with graphic design works. Kings Design encounters competition from within Nepalese-owned companies and pricing disparities. The Company is grabbing opportunities because it is providing a restaurant menu in two languages (Japanese and English), which would be a communication tool for both Nepalese cooks and Japanese customers. Besides designing, the Company provides additional services such as visa documentation support for persons planning to move to

other countries and translations into Japanese, English, Hindi, and Nepali languages. Mr. Sandesh plans to incorporate technology into graphic design.

Mr. Suman Khadka is CEO of ZOON Co., Ltd and already provided online and analog (paper printed) graphic designing services to 500+ restaurants. ZOON acknowledges the challenge of unchanged customer awareness despite the digital era, with the demand of Nepalese owners in Japan supporting documentation to the registration of a company in Japan, which is a unique business opportunity and strategy to grab other essential services such as designing, web development, application development, etc. Zoon company also successfully designs menu items in two languages: paper and digital menus. The restaurant owners and NRNA are clients of this Company with IT support. This Company focuses on endless business opportunities, mainly providing additional services beyond design, such as company registration and IT support. The Company plans to embrace digital platforms for future expansion.

Mr. Naresh Basnet is the CEO of Sinka Co., Ltd and has experience in graphic work for 1,000+ restaurants in Japan. Sinka is making it a business strategy by making one menu in Japanese and English. Besides designing, the Company is famous all over Japan for providing documentation support for Nepalese youth who want to move to a third country and translating and interpreting services accordingly. Nepalese restaurant owners have a language barrier and cannot understand the Japanese language of the cook, so they need a menu in two languages. Many Nepalese used these services to have counseling services and documents by the National Television of Japan several times, such as NHK and TVS Television, for its consulting services for people who have problems in Japan, with the request of Nepalese clients offering new services in collaboration with educational institutions to provide online

IELTS classes who want to move to Australia and Canada.

According to Mr. Kharel(2016), more than 1,800 people already from Malmavillage of Baglung. Thousands of restaurant owners are from the Baglung district of Nepal. Mr. Chhetri is one of the same district of Nepal who started his career as a graphic designer in Japan. Because of Mr. Chhetri's Japanese language ability and interest in design, his brother, Mr. Lal Bahadur ThapaChhetri, sister in law BeluKhadkaThapa, sent him for graphic training by paying charges themselves. With the motivation of his family members and some of the owners of his Baglung district,

Mr. Chhetri started a design company and, within two years, designed more than 400+ restaurants. According to Mr. Chhetri, his brother is operating a restaurant business in Japan and paying money for designing. Mr. Chhetri's family member motivated him to design a business that might be good business among Nepalese immigrants in Japan. The need for graphic designing motivated him to take graphic training, and he learned graphic designing and all related work. I took one year of graphic work training and started my own business. There are thousands of restaurant owners in my area. I started this business two years ago.

Fig. 1: Image A is the Flyer Order by the restaurant owner, and Image B is the Flyer Design according to the handwritten specific order as Image A.

Sources: Created by the author (file received to publish by Lil Bahadur ThapaChhetri)

The above image A shows a customer using writing in Roman Nepalese language, Nepalese language, and English. They can only use one particular English language or Japanese if a Japanese designing company gets this kind of order from a Nepalese customer who can complete a good design. This would be the communication tool between the customer, the restaurant staff, and the owner.

X. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

How much does it cost to design a menu? Generally, in Japan, the answer to the price of menu design determines whether a graphic design company and a Nepalese (restaurant owner) can initiate a business relationship. Regarding the price range per menu design, Nepalese designing companies charge from some thousand yen to tens of thousands in Japan. The cost of menu design can play a significant role in establishing a mutually beneficial business relationship between graphic design companies and restaurant owners.

Japanese graphic design firms with Nepalese ownership face obstacles like client migration from Japan, which is one of the negative scenarios that deal with research question no. 1. In the same way, according to the research, restaurant owners have specific requirements for menu design, including Japanese and English names and descriptions for each item on the menu. This is used for tasks other than design, like translating and creating documents in the same design place, which adds value to research question 2.

From the survey to analyze hypothesis 1 about the retention condition of Nepalese, the survey results suggest that every participant in a graphic designing company supports documentation for those who want to move to other countries from Japan. That is why Nepalese living in Japan are considering moving to a third country.

Again, regarding hypothesis 2, Nepalese owners are using graphic designing services owned by Nepalese owners for comparatively lower prices than local Japanese and making menus in dual languages. Communication between

the owner or cook and customer in dual language is vital rather than design. We got to know the people offering to design per menu price rather than a portfolio of the designers. To analyze hypothesis 3, from the survey, it was clear that Nepalese restaurant owners and cooks have problems with the Japanese language barrier. That is why they need a unique design with a dual language. Getting the same service from a Japanese Company is difficult because of language problems and pricing.

XI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Nepalese restaurants are becoming increasingly popular in Japan, and a unique aspect of this is the relationship between Nepalese restaurant owners and Nepalese design companies in Japan. The number of Nepalese restaurants is increasing daily throughout Japan due to the unique business relationship between Nepalese restaurant owners and design companies. Graphic designing companies owned by Nepalese immigrants are niche designing businesses. It is almost unique because of the unique requirements of Nepalese clients, such as dual language menus, documentation, translation, and counseling in the Nepalese language. It can be seen as a niche restaurant (Kharel, 2016). From the survey, it was clear that all business owners have a good command of Japanese and English, compared to cooks and restaurants whose background was cooking. One of the most important factors in achieving success is establishing reliable connections between clients and designing Companies. Again, the Nepalese graphic designing Company is expanding its business according to the needs of Nepalese clients in Japan. According to the survey, the Graphic design company owner and staff have a good command of the Japanese language. With the Japanese Language, they are working with local eateries and shops, which can lead to joint menu and flyer design efforts. The corporation can improve its designs by gaining a more in-depth familiarity with local standards and consumer preferences through the cultivation of these relationships.

By taking the example of image 1. As a reference, Nepalese restaurant owners or staff do not use proper order commands such as complete English Nepalese or Japanese. In the order sheet, they are using three languages(English, Nepalese Roman English, and Nepalese language). The customer expresses their idea or requirement orally.

Because of the above reasons, Japanese graphic design companies are losing their chance to enter the Nepali design industry due to language issues (English and Nepali language issues). The Nepalese community has unique social and cultural relations and a deep tie-up with the Nepalese community. However, there is a language barrier and limited information about Japanese law and other things they are operating a business. Due to the niche restaurant, they do not need a deep understanding of education and culture (Kharel, 2016). From the survey report, it was clear that Mr. Suman is helping register the Company and is doing other relevant tasks related to the restaurant and other businesses. In the same way, Mr. Tilak and Basnet support the restaurant by designing a menu with dual language,

which is the key tool to communicate between customers and the restaurant.

The owner and staff of a Nepali graphic design company are fluent in Japanese and well-versed in Japanese culture and etiquette. This knowledge and experience support the owner, cook, and their families, who may need to become more familiar with the Japanese language or culture.

Mutual support and understanding within this community are key to business success.

Depending on the purpose of this research, there was a limitation to conducting the research according to purpose. From the research, we learned that Nepalese are moving to the third country from Japan. This retention problem can be a severe problem for Nepalese and Japan because Japan is also facing a workforce shortage problem. We need to research the factors influencing the retention of Nepali talent in Japan. If there are opportunities in the future, I would like to explore these findings more deeply.

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